

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 60 (2025) 368-375

EISSN 2543-5426

Insights into the Leachates of Vermicompost and Millipede Compost

Bhagya B. Sharma¹, Kodandoor Sharathchandra² and Kandikere R. Sridhar^{2,*}

¹ Centre for Environmental Studies, Yenepoya (Deemed to be) University,
Deralakatte, Mangalore, India

² Department of Biosciences, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Mangalore, India

*E-mail address: kandikeremanasa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Liquid organic fertilizers have higher bioavailability of nutrients and are the best alternative for chemical fertilizers. In the present study, the compost leachate from earthworm (*Eudrilus eugeniae*) and pill millipede (*Arthrosphaera magna*) as byproducts has been compared for their nutrients as potential liquid fertilizers. The compost was prepared from pre-digested leaf litter and cow dung (60:40, w/w). The leachate collection commenced 15 days after the setup and continued on 25, 35, 45, 55, and 65 days. The dark amber-colored vermicompost leachate (VCL) and honey-colored pill millipede compost leachate (MCL) collected were analyzed for physicochemical composition. Pre-digested organic material without earthworms or millipedes served as a control (CL). Results indicate that VCL shows a higher value than MCL and the CL for conductivity, TDS, salinity, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, and sodium. Nitrogen content and other nutrients were high in MCL, making it a good supplement. The C/N ratio of CL drastically reduced in VCL and MCL, facilitating quick availability of nitrogen. Given the increasing demand for liquid organic fertilizers due to their ease of application and high nutrient availability, both VCL and MCL serve as effective organic fertilizers.

Keywords: Decomposition, Earthworms, liquid fertilizers, Millipedes, Minerals, Organic matter

1. INTRODUCTION

Organic agriculture has gained momentum in the recent past. Farmers are shifting towards sustainable organic farming as there is demand for products that are grown and certified organically. It has been shown by several studies that organically grown foods are devoid of harmful pesticides and heavy metals. Studies have also reported higher biodiversity in fields with organic farming than in the conventional crop fields [1]. The European Union has set a target of 25% of agricultural land to be managed organically by the year 2030 [2]. Similarly, Sweden is targeting 30% of the total production area to be organically certified, while India holds 30% of total organic produce in the world [3]. Organic production depends on the plant and animal waste as a source of nutrients by preparing compost or manures. There are several parameters for selection and evaluation of compost quality [4-6].

Recently the demand for liquid organic fertilizers is gaining momentum due to added advantages in agriculture, pest control, and greenhouse production [7-11]. Various types of organic cocktails are prepared by the farmers, such as panchagavya, jeevamrutha, and vermiwash, while cow urine is also used as liquid fertilizers [12, 13]. Among the leachates, vermiwash holds a unique place as it is organic, inexpensive, eco-friendly, and a rich source of nutrients [14]. Vermiwash is a liquid containing earthworm mucus, nutrients, microorganisms, and plant growth-promoting constituents [15]. It is also rich in amino acids, vitamins, hormones (auxins and cytokinins), and minerals (nitrogen, potassium, magnesium, zinc, calcium, iron, and copper) [16, 17]. Vermiwash could be produced by different methods, such as the heat or the cold stress [17]. Another technique is that earthworms are stirred for a few minutes in lukewarm water or ice-cold water, then released into water at room temperature and later transferred back into the vermicompost unit [18]. Besides, layering earthworms along with gravel, sand, vermicompost, and pre-digested organic matter, water is allowed to trickle down through the layers slowly to collect vermiwash [3, 17]. Similar to vermicompost (vermiwash), millipede compost (its compost wash) is yet to be practiced on a large scale.

The composition of vermiwash depends on the raw materials used in composting and the method of vermiwash preparation. Similar to earthworms, the pill millipedes as saprophagous fauna are good decomposers of organic waste as they mineralize organic matter, aerate the soils, and contribute to soil fertility [19-21]. Studies on pill millipede compost have been carried out and demonstrated a positive effect on plant growth [22, 23]. Moreover, maintenance of millipede compost units is easier than vermicomposting. Organic liquid fertilizers are beneficial due to the bioavailability of the nutrients, minerals and ease of application. The nutrients are readily available compared to solid composts and also reduce the risks of leaching or surface runoff. They are also useful in plant protection against plant pathogens. In this study, we have compared the physicochemical constituents of two liquid organic leachates (vermiwash and millipede compost wash) for their potential application.

2. METHODS

2. 1. Leachates

The earthen pots were used for the production of the compost in three replicates (Figure 1a). The base of the pot was covered with large-sized gravel and coconut coir for aeration. The raw materials for the compost were pre-digested leaf litter and cow dung (60:40, w/w). The

contents were mixed thoroughly, watered, and left for two days. The composting pots were prevented from direct exposure to sunlight. After two days of setup, 30 adult earthworms (*Eudrilus eugeniae*) were released into each unit for composting (Figure 1b). Similarly, 10 adult millipedes (*Arthrosphaera magna*) were introduced into each unit to produce millipede compost (Figure 1c). The pots were covered by wire nets to protect them from predators. The contents of the pot were gently mixed once every three days. Water was sprinkled every three days to maintain 70-80% moisture content. The experimental setup was allowed to act for 65 days, when the organic material was converted into dark granular compost. The same treatments for compost pots without animals served as a control. Sprinkling water every three days will allow the accumulation of the trickled water passing through the compost. The leachates were collected from the pots through an outlet (Figure 1d). The leachate collection started 15 days after the setup and subsequently 25, 35, 45, 55, and 65 days later. They were preserved in a refrigerator, and pooled extracts in triplicate were assessed for physicochemical characteristics.

Fig. 1(a-d). (a) Setup of compost pot; (b) vermicompost pot; (c) millipede compost pot; (d) collection of compost leachate from millipede compost.

2. 2. Nutrient analysis

The pH, conductivity, total dissolved solids (TDS), and salinity were assessed using a water analyzer (#371, Systronics India Ltd., Ahmadabad, Gujarat). Organic carbon (Walkley and Black's titration), total nitrogen (micro-Kjeldahl), and phosphorus (ascorbic acid method) were evaluated based on the methods by Jackson [24]. Organic matter was determined by the titrimetric method [25]. The rest of the minerals were assessed by the field-emission scanning electron microscope-energy dispersive spectrometer analysis (SEM-EDS) (FESEM Carl Zeiss, Oxford Instruments, USA) [26]. The C/N ratio of composts was calculated based on total carbon and nitrogen.

2. 3. Data analysis

Differences in various parameters control vs. leachates and between leachates were evaluated by a *t*-test by Statistica, Version # 8 [27].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physicochemical characteristics of control leachate (CL), vermicompost leachate (VCL), and millipede compost leachate (MCL) have been compared (Table 1). There is a drastic difference in physicochemical features among leachates. The pH, conductivity, TDS, total carbon, potassium, magnesium, and sodium significantly differed between CL vs. VCL and MCL. Salinity, organic carbon, calcium, silicon, and chlorine significantly differed between CL and VCL. Organic matter, total nitrogen, aluminum, and chromium significantly differed between CL and MCL. Conductivity, TDS, salinity, organic carbon, organic matter, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, sodium, manganese, silicon, chlorine, and sulfur were significantly higher in VCL than in MCL. The pH, total nitrogen, iron, and chromium were significantly higher in MCL than in VCL.

Table 1. Physicochemical composition of vermicompost and millipede compost (n = 3, mean ±SD; *t*-test: control vs. leachates, *, p<0.05, **, p<0.01, ***, p<0.001; *t*-test: between leachates, #, p<0.05, ##, p<0.01, ###, p<0.001) (BDL, below detectable limit; NP, not present).

	Control leachate (CL)	Vermicompost leachate (VCL)	Millipede compost leachate (MCL)
pH	6.84±0.05	6.54±0.09*	7.09±0.16**
Conductivity (µS/cm)	785.76±7.58	2512.66±40.26***###	875.83±11.33***
TDS (mg/l)	68.46±0.94	594±15.09***###	52.3±6.36*
Salinity (ppt.)	0.02±0.00	0.57±0.02***###	0.04±0.005
Organic carbon (%)	6.26±0.09	3.13±0.30*#	2.67±0.15
Total carbon (%)	29.17±0.99	24.26±1.43***	25.47±0.81***

Organic matter (%)	9.84±0.30	5.4±0.52 [#]	4.61±0.26 [*]
Total nitrogen (%)	1.15±0.03	7.18±0.22	8.25±0.11 ^{****#}
Phosphorous (%)	0.78±0.03	1.39±0.16 ^{##}	0.20±0.02
Potassium (%)	1.18±0.03	2.85±0.07 ^{****}	0.80±0.02 ^{**}
Calcium (%)	0.47±0.04	1.77±0.07 ^{****##}	0.34±0.02
Magnesium (%)	1.12±0.06	2.14±0.07 ^{****##}	0.35 0.03 ^{**}
Sodium (%)	1.39±0.04	2.96±0.16 ^{****}	0.02±0.01 [*]
Manganese (%)	0.002±0.001	0.04±0.01 [#]	BDL
Iron (%)	0.04±0.01	0.05±0.007	0.39±0.03 ^{###}
Copper (%)	BDL	BDL	NP
Zinc (%)	0.006±0.001	0.01±0.005	0.01±0.01
Selenium (%)	NP	BDL	NP
Silicon (%)	0.06±0.01	0.87±0.05 ^{****##}	0.06±0.02
Chlorine (%)	0.52±0.04	0.86±0.060 ^{****}	NP
Aluminum (%)	0.001±0.00	NP	0.01±0.01 [*]
Chromium (%)	0.001±0.00	NP	0.01±0.002 ^{###}
Sulfur (%)	0.28±0.03	0.89±0.03 ^{###}	BDL
C/N ratio	25.4	3.4	3.1

If the soil is acidic or alkaline, the nutrients will not dissolve, and they are not available to the host plants [7]. In our study, the pH of control and experimental groups was conducive to plant growth. The VCL has significantly higher conductivity compared to control and MCL, suggesting it has more dissolved ionic substances, which enhances the nutrient availability. Conductivity and TDS in VCL were exceptionally high, indicating it might introduce excess ions or salts into the soil. High conductivity can help in soil bioremediation and plant growth when applied appropriately (e.g., soil particle flocculation, leaching of sodium deep into soil, and cation exchange capacity) [28]. The VCL exhibits significantly higher salinity compared to CL and MCL, which could affect plant growth depending on salinity tolerance. The leachates with low salinity will be suitable for foliar spray to control plant pathogens [3, 9]. The VCL and MCL possess lower total carbon and organic carbon than CL, denoting decreased carbon in leachates. These organic fertilizers are also suitable for greenhouse production systems [10].

The presence of organic matter and its decomposition releases nutrients, retains moisture, and is important for the resilience of the soil [7]. Among three leachates, phosphorus,

potassium, calcium, magnesium, sodium, manganese, zinc, silicon, chlorine, and sulfur were higher in VCL, showing its richness in minerals. Aluminum and chromium were present only in CL and MCL. The VCL and MCL possess higher total nitrogen content than CL, indicating enrichment of soil and supply of nitrogen to host plants. Nitrogen content in MCL is the highest, which might supplement more nitrogen to plants. In addition, the C/N ratio has reduced drastically in VCL and MCL, facilitating further availability of nitrogen to the host plants. Although some studies are available on pill millipede compost [19-22], no information is available on their compost leachate. However, as there are no studies on MCL, further insights are necessary towards using it in hydroponics and greenhouse trials.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the potential of vermicompost leachate (VCL) and millipede compost leachate (MCL) as potential organic liquid fertilizers. Both leachates exhibit optimum pH, ensuring nutrient availability for plant growth. The VCL is distinct with high conductivity, total dissolved solids, salinity, and minerals (phosphorous, potassium, calcium, magnesium, and sodium), making it an effective liquid fertilizer. The MCL possesses high nitrogen content, making it an excellent supplement for soil enrichment. Drastic reduction of C/N ratio between control and experimental leachates shows additional supply of nitrogen to host plants. These leachates are the byproducts of composts and have potential applications in plant production employing hydroponics with appropriate modifications. This is the first report on pill millipede compost leachate study and comparison with VCL. The findings brought out the potential of VCL and MCL as sustainable alternatives against chemical fertilizers to improve the soil health and crop productivity.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support of the Department of Biosciences, Mangalore University, and Yenepoya University, for field laboratory facilities.

References

- [1] Tscharrntke T, Grass I, Wanger TC, Westphal C, Batáry P. Beyond organic farming - harnessing biodiversity-friendly landscapes. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution* 2021; 36: 919-930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2021.06.010>
- [2] Paull J. Organic Agriculture in Europe: EU Sets Goal of Growing Organic Farmland from 10% to 25% by 2030. *European Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences* 2024; 6: 26-31
- [3] Nandhini DU, Venmathi T. Vermiwash-A potential plant growth promoter. *AgricINTERNATIONAL* 2017; 4(1): 27. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2454-8634.2017.00006.7>
- [4] Brinton WF. Compost quality standards & Guidelines. New York State Association of Recyclers, Woods End Research Laboratory, Inc., USA, 2000; p. 42.

- [5] Sharma A, Ganguly R, Gupta AK. Spectral characterization and quality assessment of organic compost for agricultural purposes. *International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture* 2019; 8: 197-213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40093-018-0233-7>
- [6] Peña H, Mendza H, Diáñez F, Santos M. Parameter Selection for the Evaluation of Compost Quality. *Agronomy* 2020; 10, 1567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10101567>
- [7] Zarei M, Abadi VAJM, Moridi A. Comparison of vermiwash and vermicompost tea properties produced from different organic beds under greenhouse conditions. *International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture* 2018; 7: 25-32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40093-017-0186-2>
- [8] Deepthi MP, Niveditha S, Saminathan K, Narendhirakannan TT, Karmegam N, Kathireswari P. Effect of vermiwash prepared from livestock biowaste as vermiponics medium on the growth and biochemical indices of *Amaranthus viridis* L. *Environmental Technology & Innovation* 2021; 21: 1-12, 101300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2020.101300>
- [9] Gudeta K, Julka JM, Kumar A, Bhagat A, Kumari A. Vermiwash: An agent of disease and pest control in soil, a review. *Heliyon* 2021; 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06434>
- [10] Karl-Johan Bergstrand. Organic fertilizers in greenhouse production systems – a review, *Scientia Horticulturae*, Volume 295, 2022, 110855, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2021.110855>
- [11] Rajapaksha, R.M.P.I., Vibodhani, D.D.N., Harshana, M.M.J. *et al.* Effect of organic fertilizer solutions on the growth and yield of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.). *Org. Agr.* 14, 513–522 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-024-00478-1>
- [12] Boraiah B, Devakumar N, Shubha S, Palanna KB. Effect of Panchagavya, Jeevamrutha and cow urine on beneficial microorganisms and yield of capsicum (*Capsicum annum* L. var. *grossum*). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 2017; 6(8): 3226-3234. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2017.609.397>
- [13] Shukla AK, Singh RR, Mishra T, Tripathi KM, Shukla S, Singh S. evaluation of bio dynamic compost and bio dynamic compost wash on growth and yield of rice. *International Journal of Plant and Soil Science* 2023; 35: 892-902
- [14] Singh T, Kapila R, Kumar M.. A minireview on vermicompost and vermiwash as green pesticide for sustainable crop production: Approaches, applications, and advancements. *JSA Reports* 2024; 4: 4-10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsf2.172>
- [15] Gopal M, Gupta A, Palaniswami C, Dhanapal R, Thomas GV Coconut leaf vermiwash: a bio-liquid from coconut leaf vermicompost for improving the crop production capacities of soil. *Current Science* 2010; 98: 1202-1210.
- [16] Suthar S. Evidence of plant hormone like substances in vermiwash: an ecologically safe option of synthetic chemicals for sustainable farming. *Ecological Engineering* 2010; 36: 1089-1092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2010.04.027>

- [17] Meena AL, Karwal M, Raghavendra KJ, Kumari P. Vermiwash: A potential tool for sustainable organic farming, *Food and Scientific Reports* 2021; <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.35686>
- [18] Patil RP, Biradar PM. Coelomic fluid extraction and coelomocytes count in different epigeic earthworms. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research* 2023; 14: 22-29
- [19] Ashwini KM, Sridhar KR. Leaf litter preference and conversion by a saprophagous tropical pill millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* Attems. *Pedobiologia* 2005; 49: 307-316
- [20] Ashwini KM, Sridhar KR. Breakdown of plantation residues by pill millipedes (*Arthrosphaera magna*) and assessment of compost quality. *Current Science* 2006; 90: 954-959.
- [21] Sridhar KR, Ambarish CN. Pill-millipede compost: A viable alternative to utilize urban organic solid wastes. *Current Science* 2013; 104, 1543-1547
- [22] Ashwini KM, Sridhar KR. Evaluation of pill millipede (*Arthrosphaera magna*) compost on plant growth and dry matter yield. *Electronic Journal of Environmental, Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 2006; 5: 1323-1329
- [23] Ambarish CN, Sridhar KR. Production and quality of pill-millipede manure: A microcosm study. *Agricultural Research* 2013; 2: 258-264
- [24] Jackson ML. Soil Chemical Analysis. Prentice Hall International, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey, USA 1973; p. 498.
- [25] Sestu S, Bekele T. Procedure for soil and plant analysis. National Soil Research Centre, Ethiopian Agricultural Research Organization, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia 2000; p. 110.
- [26] Ramamurthy N, Kannan S. SEM-EDS analysis of soil and plant (*Calotropis gigantea* Linn.) collected from an industrial village, Cuddalore Dt., Tamil Nadu, India. *Romanian Journal of Biophysics* 2009; 19: 219-226
- [27] StatSoft Inc. Statistica Version # 8. Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA 2008.
- [28] Gondek M, Weindorf DC, Thiel C, Kleinheinz G. Soluble Salts in Compost and Their Effects on Soil and Plants: A Review. *Compost Science & Utilization* 2020; 28: 59-75